

**SPATIO-TEMPORAL VARIATION OF TROPOSPHERIC NITROGEN
DIOXIDE OVER SOUTHWEST NIGERIA**

BY

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CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that this research project is an original work undertaken by OJETUNDE MICHAEL MONJOLAOLUWA with Matric Number MCS/16/7394 under the supervision of Dr. Ademola Akinbobola. and has been prepared in accordance with the regulations governing the preparation of projects in the Department of Meteorology and Climate Science, Federal University of Technology, Akure. This project has been read and approved by:

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ACKNOWLEDGMENT

I wish to acknowledge the faithful God for the love, protection, guidance and mercies through the course of this programme.

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DEDICATION

This research project is dedicated to Almighty God who made it possible for me to start and end another phase of life in joy.

ABSTRACT

Emissions of Nitrogen dioxide from biomass burning, soil microbial processes, and anthropogenic and gas flaring activities over Southwest Nigeria play a major role in local and regional air quality. The study investigates the spatiotemporal trend of NO₂ using Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS) data between 2010 and 2020. An average of 3.97×10^{15} mol/cm² with an increase of 7.63% over the years was discovered in the course of the study. The increase in the pollutant over this region is linked to Industrial processes, biomass burning and anthropogenic activities like vehicular emission, increase in industrial and agricultural activities, etc. The Spatio-temporal trend analysis showed significant decline in areas where biomass burning was the main driver of NO₂ variability and a significant increase in areas where urban emission was the main driver. The observed seasonality of NO₂ is associated with change in meteorological conditions and seasonal cycles anthropogenic emissions. The analysis revealed a monthly peak in January followed by September largely linked to meteorological conditions, Industrial processes and anthropogenic emissions from crop residue and biomass and low concentration is mostly attributed to meteorological conditions.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of Study

Air pollution is a common theme for the past decades because of its growing sources. The most common sources are anthropogenic activities and deforestation in the developing countries of the world. The major pollutants from diesel fuel vehicles include carbon monoxide (CO) and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) from which secondary pollutant, tropospheric ozone (O₃) is formed. (charron et al., 2003).

Nitrogen is essential for all living things. Little of the world's nitrogen is found in the solid earth within the chemical structure of rock, soil, and sediment. The remainder moves in a dynamic cycle involving the atmosphere, oceans, lakes, streams, plants, and animals. Small amounts of the nitrogen in soil and sediment also enter this complex cycle.

Nitrogen oxides (NO_x) play critical roles in many atmospheric processes including the catalytic production of tropospheric ozone and the formation of nitric acid being key elements of local air quality with effects felt across global tropospheric chemistry (Richter et al., 2005). Atmospheric pollution affects human and ecosystem health as well as being intrinsically linked to climate in the present and coming decades (von Schneidemesser et al., 2015). NO₂ is a pollutant and key precursor for tropospheric Ozone (O₃) formation (Monks et al., 2015) and has both anthropogenic (fossil fuel / bio-fuel burning and incomplete combustion) and natural sources (soil emissions). Southwest Nigeria is an area with a high concentration of industrial activities and urbanization, which can contribute to high levels of NO₂ in the region. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), Nigeria has one of the highest levels of air pollution in Africa, with particulate matter (PM) and NO₂ being major contributors. This situation is exacerbated by the growing population, rapid urbanization, and lack of

effective air quality management policies. Therefore, understanding the spatiotemporal variation of tropospheric NO₂ over Southwest Nigeria is crucial for effective air quality management.

Nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) is one of the major air pollutants and is strongly related to population density (Lamsal et al., 2013). As such it is a significant environmental issue in many large urban agglomerations (Schneider and van der A, 2012; Liu and Zhu, 2013; Hilboll et al., 2013; Guerrero et al., 2014). It is associated with health issues such as airway inflammation and reductions in lung function (World Health Organization, 2013). However, station observations of NO₂ are relatively rare on a global scale, and in particular in developing countries, and thus are not able to provide a global and spatially continuous perspective. Even in areas with relatively large numbers of air quality monitoring stations such as in Europe and the United States, the station density is often quite low. Satellite observations on the other hand offer a unique opportunity for studying the continuous spatial patterns and the temporal dynamics of the constituents affecting air quality in general (Martin, 2008; Burrows et al., 2011; Lahoz et al., 2012; Duncan et al., 2014) and of tropospheric NO₂ in particular (Richter et al., 2005; Martin 2008; van der A et al., 2008; Zhou et al., 2012; Castellanos and Boersma, 2012; Schneider and van der A, 2012; Hilboll et al., 2013; Curier et al., 2014).

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Oxides of nitrogen (NO and NO₂) in the chemistry of the atmosphere is to be noted for their roles in the formation of earth's ozone in the stratosphere (10-50km). Its set of catalytic reactions transfers ozone to molecular oxygen which is effective above 24km.

Despite the importance of NO₂ as an air pollutant and its potential impact on human health, there are limited information on the spatiotemporal variation of tropospheric NO₂ over Southwest Nigeria. This information is critical for effective air quality management, as it helps to identify the areas with high levels of NO₂ and the sources of the pollutant. The lack of data on the spatiotemporal variation of tropospheric NO₂ over Southwest Nigeria makes it difficult for policymakers to develop effective air

quality management strategies and interventions to reduce the concentration of NO₂ in the region. Therefore, there is a need to investigate the spatiotemporal variation of tropospheric NO₂ over Southwest Nigeria using satellite remote sensing data.

Unfortunately, because of NO₂'s high oxidizing power which is closely linked to the formation of other pollutants including the tropospheric ozone, it is difficult to establish its benefits to human, plants and the immediate environment meteorologically.

1.3 Aim

The aim of this research is to evaluate temporal variation of tropospheric nitrogen dioxide over Southwest Nigeria.

1.4 Research Objectives

The specific objectives of the study are to determine the:

- inter-annual changes in the concentration of the pollutant
- effect of temperature, wind and precipitation in the seasonal variation of the NO₂.
- spatiotemporal distribution of the NO₂.

1.5 Justification of the Study

This study investigates the mechanism that drives the variability of the concentration of NO₂ over the study area and how best the concentration could be reduced.

1.6 Contribution to Knowledge

This research is expected to provide information to make informed decisions on meaningful ways to mitigate the production and transportation of NO₂, its emission and its hotspots over Southwest Nigeria because of its hazardous nature.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

Nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) is a major constituent of the air pollution mix. It depends on land surface exchanges of nitrogen and oxygen compounds. Deposition and emission fluxes of nitrogen compounds are poorly quantified, and are likely to increase in the near future due to land use change and anthropogenic pressure. This chapter explains the current knowledge of the pollutant in Southwest Nigeria. It may be interesting to expressly review literatures that cover the origin, physical and the chemistry behind the variability of the pollutant in the study area.

2.2 Emission of NO₂

All over the world, NO₂ gets into the atmosphere primarily by the combustion of fossil fuel. It is formed from emissions from vehicles, power plants and plants. Nitrogen oxides (NO_x = NO + NO₂) are released through combustion of fossil fuel, biomass burning, lightning and microbiological processes in the soil (Lee et al., 1997; HSDB, 2007; Seinfeld and Pandis, 2008).

On an average about 50% of NO_x is released from industry and traffic and 20% from biomass burning (Oliver et al., 1998; Seinfeld and Pandis, 2008). Among natural emissions, approximately 10% are through lightning while 15% are from soil due to microbial activities (Lee et al., 1997; Seinfeld and Pandis, 2008). Subject to the different meteorological conditions, seasons, actinic flux and concentrations of the hydroxyl (OH) radical, the lifetime of NO_x ranges from a few hours to 1 day (Crutzen, 1979; Beirle et al., 2003; Platt and Stutz, 2004; Seinfeld and Pandis, 2008). NO₂ is a strong oxidant and has been listed as a critical pollutant (Seinfeld and Pandis, 2008). It plays a crucial role in tropospheric chemistry mainly involved in the formation of secondary air pollutants (photochemical smog) and acid rain (Logan et al., 1981; Thompson, 1992; Seinfeld and Pandis, 2008).

Tropospheric NO₂ shows high spatiotemporal variability mainly modulated by local emission changes, seasonal cycles, and meteorological conditions. Southwest Nigeria experiences severe air quality degradation due to high population growth rate, burgeoning urbanization and industrialization, expanding demand of agricultural products, and exponentially increasing energy consumption rate (Azad et al., 1998; Ghose et al., 2004; Badarinath et al., 2006, 2009).

Therefore, in order to develop the effective strategies to reduce its emissions, it is necessary to assess spatiotemporal distribution of NO₂ and identify its emission sources. Southwest Nigeria is known to generate large amounts of pollutants from transportation, industrial process, power generation and domestic activities. Urban vehicular pollution is also rather high in urban Southwest Nigeria owing to the high usage of often poorly maintained second hand cars and low-quality fuel (Schwela, 2009). It has been estimated that in addition to seasonal biomass burning which releases NO₂ and pyrogenic carbon into the atmosphere (Lehsten et al., 2009) directly, soil emissions of NO_x represent 15% of global N emissions (Hudman et al., 2012).

Some researchers have also found large emissions of rain-induced NO_x (NO+NO₂) from the soil following long periods of drought in savannahs and seasonally dry forests (Jaegle et al., 2005; Feig et al., 2008; Hudman et al., 2010; Kim et al., 2012) and a strong link between this soil-released NO_x and atmospheric NO₂ (Jaegle' et al., 2005; Delon et al., 2015). Microbial activities lead to denitrification and nitrification in the soil resulting in the formation of soil gases such as NO (Delon et al., 2015). Kim et al. (2012) explained that root secretions from reviving plants following rewetting could significantly affect the soil surface flux of soil gases like NO. Water-stressed bacteria become active as soon as water drops on the dry soil (Hudman et al., 2012) and feed on nutrients which have accumulated in dry season or longer periods between irregular/sporadic rainfalls (Meixner and Yang, 2006). NO is also produced rapidly after N (Nitrogen) fertilizers (both livestock manure and synthetic fertilizer) are applied to the soil to improve agricultural outputs (Pilegaard, 2013). The NO emissions from these microbial/bacterial activities and nitrification of the soil through fertilizers are released to

the atmosphere through pulsing and oxidized in a reaction with O₃ in the atmosphere to form NO₂ (Pilegaard, 2013) especially in strongly sunlit areas of semi-aridity (Delon et al., 2008).

2.3 Deposition of NO₂

The effect of NO₂ in the atmosphere depends solely on how it is distributed through the environment. Deposition of chemical species onto the Earth's surface plays an essential role in controlling the concentration of gases and aerosols in the troposphere. Studying of deposition thus allows for tracing the temporal and spatial evolution of atmospheric chemistry and is a pertinent indicator for evaluating natural and anthropogenic influences. The deposition of atmospheric nitrogen (N) species constitutes a major nutrient input to the biosphere. On a long-term scale, the increase of N inputs into terrestrial or aquatic ecosystems leads to important environmental consequences such as a loss of biodiversity, eutrophication, acidification of seminatural ecosystems, leaching of nitrate into groundwater and increased carbon storage (Vitousek et al., 1997; Rodhe et al., 2002; Bobbink et al., 1998; Bouwman et al., 2002b; Liu et al., 2013).

Monitoring networks have been established around the world to measure wet and dry deposition. The international program Deposition of Biogeochemically Important Trace Species (DEBITS) was initiated in 1990 as part of International Global Atmospheric Chemistry/International Geosphere-Biosphere Programme (IGAC/IGBP) "core project" in order to study wet and dry atmospheric deposition in tropical regions (Lacaux et al., 2003). The DEBITS network collects data from 25 stations that are distributed within the tropical belt in Africa, Asia and South America, and results are presented in the new IGAC structure or DEBITS II (Pienaar et al., 2005; Bates et al., 2006). For tropical Africa, the IDAF (IGAC/DEBITS/AFRICA) project started in 1994 and was implemented in partnership with INSU (Institut National des Sciences de l'Univers, in France) and the CNRS (Centre National de la

Recherche Scientifique, in France) as part of the Environmental Research Observatory (ORE, in France) networks.

The main objectives of IDAF are to measure wet and dry deposition fluxes and to identify the relative contribution of natural and anthropogenic sources, as well as the factors regulating these fluxes. IDAF activity is based on high-quality measurements of atmospheric chemical data (gaseous, precipitation and aerosol chemical compositions) on the basis of multiyear monitoring. Within the framework of IDAF, several studies of precipitation chemical composition representative of great African ecosystems have been recently published (Galy-Lacaux and Modi, 1998; Galy-Lacaux et al., 2001, 2009; Al-Ourabi and Lacaux, 2002; Lacaux et al., 1993, 2003; Sigha et al., 2003; Yoboue et al., 2005; Mphepya et al., 2004; 2006; Laouali et al., 2012).

Atmospheric nitrogen compounds cycle to the land and water through atmospheric deposition. Wet deposition, predominantly rain, fog and snow, carries nitrate and ammonium. Dry deposition involves complex interactions between airborne nitrogen compounds and plant, water, soil, rock, or building surfaces.

2.3.1 Wet Deposition

Nitrogen oxides contribute to acid rain, it is important in the formation of both acid precipitation and photochemical smog and it causes nitrogen loading.

M represents the inert molecule which absorbs some of the excess energy of the reaction which is generally N₂ in the atmosphere. NO₂ is formed by the oxidization of no in the atmosphere and reacts with OH

These acids may deposit in places other than water such as snow and fog. The lower temperature at high altitudes causes water vapour to condense out of the atmosphere, forming a moist blanket of acidic fog which surrounds trees.

It also removes most of the aerosols containing SO_4^{2-} , NO_3^- and NH_4^+ , but can be captured directly at the terrestrial surface by aerodynamically rough surfaces e.g. forests. Since rainfall essentially removes these aerosols, parts of the region with the largest wet deposition tend to be areas with high rainfall.

Figure 2.1: Pollutant and deposition processes
Source: Air Pollution Information System Website

2.3.2 Dry Deposition

Nitrogen deposition on the terrestrial surface impacts both atmospheric chemistry and ecosystem dynamics. Ammonia (NH_3), Nitrogen dioxide (NO_2) and Nitric acid (HNO_3) are the most important contributors to Nitrogen dry deposition (Trebs et al., 2006). Dry deposition involves complex interactions between airborne nitrogen compounds and plant, water, soil, rock, or building surfaces.

Direct measurement of NO_2 dry deposition flux can be made using techniques such as eddy covariance flux from towers or aircraft (Wesely and Hicks, 2000) or dynamic chambers (Breuninger et al., 2012).

In practical terms, these measurements are relatively rare. Measurements of NO₂ flux in particular are difficult to interpret because of possible chemical flux divergences (Kramm et al., 1995; Heal et al., 2001; Horii et al., 2004). NO_x emissions that affect net atmosphere-biosphere fluxes (Ganzeveld et al., 2002; Duyzer et al., 2004), with a possible NO₂ leaf compensation point (Lerdau et al., 2000; Chaparro-Suarez et al., 2011; Breuninger et al., 2013), and local advection (Stella et al., 2012).

Dry deposition flux of NO₂ is often determined by inferential modelling techniques, which use modelled dry deposition velocities in combination with measured in situ surface concentrations and some basic micrometeorological and surface cover parameters to determine surface fluxes. The dry deposition flux F_d of an atmospheric constituent to the Earth's surface is typically defined as the product of a dry deposition velocity V_d and the constituent's surface concentration C_s using

$$F_d = -V_d C_s \quad 2.3$$

where V_d depends on properties of the constituent, local meteorology, transport above the surface, and surface properties such as vegetative and soil uptake. The inferential model approach has been used to determine deposition at individual measurement sites (Schwede et al., 2011; Flechard et al., 2011; Delon et al., 2012) and to estimate regional deposition ratios and patterns using multiple sites (Baumgardner et al., 2002; Holland et al., 2005; Zhang et al., 2005). Estimates of regional scale deposition budgets can be hindered by the sparse coverage of measurement sites and biases from site locations near or far from local sources of NO₂. Ideally, true regional deposition budgets would be calculated using continuous spatial measurements of surface concentration. One approach that has been used over Europe (Holland et al., 2005) and China (Lü and Tian, 2007) for NO₂ applies a geospatial interpolation scheme to ambient concentration measurements to infer continuous concentration fields. An alternative approach uses a regional or global model to produce maps of dry

deposition and uses in situ measurements to assess those results (Ganzeveld and Lelieveld, 1995; Ganzeveld et al., 1998; Dentener et al., 2006; Zhang et al., 2012; Ellis et al., 2013).

Figure 2.2: Transportation of NO₂
Source: Environmental chemistry slide lecture note

2.4 NO₂ and Meteorological Variables

Increased air pollutant concentrations in the urban environment do not typically result from sudden increases in emissions, but rather from meteorological conditions that impede dispersion in the atmosphere or result in increased pollutant generation (Gorai et al, 2015; Cheng et al, 2007). There are many aspects of variations in air pollution that are still difficult to understand. One of these aspects is the estimation of the sensitivity of air pollutants to individual meteorological parameters. A combination of meteorological variables important to these conditions include temperature, winds, radiation, atmospheric moisture, and mixing depth (Gorai et al, 2015). It is well known that concentrations of pollutant within local air sheds are affected by meteorological parameters (Elminir

2005; Ordonez et al., 2005; Beaver et al., 2009). Meteorological conditions play a crucial role in ambient air pollution by affecting both directly and indirectly the emissions, transport, formation, and deposition of air pollutants. Several research studies pertaining to weather and atmospheric pollution effects on humans have established associations between meteorological conditions and parameters to air pollutants. Some studies have provided evidence that meteorological factors can significantly affect air quality (Elminir, 2005; Beaver et al., 2009; Zhang et al., 2015; Csavina et al., 2014).

The relationship between traffic related air pollutants and meteorological parameters can provide important information about air pollution. The wind speeds may transport air pollutants (O_3 , CO, NO_x) from distant sources. There are negative correlation between air pollutants concentration and wind speed data. Analysis of the surface wind speed and direction alone will not adequately explain the variability in the concentrations of air pollutants. The association between temperature and NO_x are found to be important. For NO_x higher concentrations occur at lower ambient temperature in winter season. Daily polluting concentrations are not only influenced by daily meteorological parameters but also by the values of previous day. There has been direct link between NO_x concentration and their previous day's concentration (Ocak, 1997). The most important role of meteorology is in the dispersion, transformation and removal of air pollutants from atmosphere (Gurjar et al., 2008).

2.5 Tropospheric NO_2 Measurements

Nitrogen dioxide (NO_2) is one of the pollutants regulated by the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), as it is detrimental to human health and ecosystems (EPA, 2009). Major sources of NO_x include combustion, soil emissions, and lightning. Tropospheric NO_2 concentrations are highly variable in space and time due to spatial heterogeneity of NO_x sources and the relatively short lifetime of NO_x in the lower troposphere.

NO_2 is measured locally by in situ monitors and detected remotely in an atmospheric column by ground-based and satellite instruments. NO_2 observations from satellite offer a globally consistent data

set, albeit at coarse resolutions of 10s to 100s of kilometres, enabling a wide range of applications including many not feasible from in situ observations.

Several studies have used satellite observations of NO₂ to evaluate chemical transport models (Martin et al., 2002; van Noije et al., 2006; Lamsal et al., 2008; Kim et al., 2009; Herron- Thorpe et al., 2010), examine spatial and temporal patterns of NO_x emissions (Beirle et al., 2003; Richter et al., 2005; Kim et al., 2006; Boersma et al., 2008a; Hilboll et al., 2013; Russell et al., 2010, 2012; Duncan et al., 2013), examine NO_x sources (Jaeglé et al., 2005; van der A et al., 2008; Bucsela et al., 2010; de Wildt et al., 2012; Lin, 2012; Ghude et al., 2010, 2013a), provide top-down constraints on surface NO_x emissions (Martin et al., 2003; Konovalov et al., 2006; Lin et al., 2010; Lamsal et al., 2011; Ghude et al., 2013b), infer NO_x lifetimes (Schaub et al., 2007; Lamsal et al., 2010; Beirle et al., 2011), and estimate surface NO₂ concentrations (Lamsal et al., 2008, 2013; Bechle et al., 2013). The quality of the satellite data directly affects every one of these applications and estimates. Careful assessments of the accuracy of retrievals with credible, coincident, independent measurements help ensure reliable analyses.

Observations of tropospheric NO₂ which has a short atmospheric lifetime (from several hours in summer to tens of hours in winter (Beirle et al., 2003; Lamsal et al., 2010), provide key information about emission sources of air pollutants and air quality. The strong absorption lines of the NO₂ molecule in the visible wavelength range of the spectrum facilitate the use of optical absorption spectroscopy for measuring atmospheric NO₂ abundances. Nadir viewing instruments have been deployed on satellite platforms since the mid-1990s. This has resulted in the global monitoring of NO concentrations under consistent measurement conditions (Burrows et al., 2011).

For measurements of tropospheric NO₂, the nadir viewing Global Ozone Monitoring Experiment (GOME, on board ERS-2, 40×320 km² ground pixel size), which measured from 1995-2003, the Scanning Imaging Absorption spectrometer for Atmospheric Chartography (SCIAMACHY, on board ENVISAT, 30×60 km²; Burrows et al., 1995), measured from 2002-2012, the Ozone Monitoring Instrument (OMI, on board AURA, 13×24 km²), measures from 2004 till present, and GOME's

operational meteorological successor GOME-2 (on board Metop-A1, $40 \times 80 \text{ km}^2$), measures from 2006 till present, provide measurements of the upwelling radiance suitable for retrieval of tropospheric NO_2 . These four instruments provide a continuous time series of tropospheric NO_2 measurements beginning in August 1995. The long-term data set from these instruments provides a unique reference for monitoring changes in global tropospheric NO_2 distributions (Richter et al., 2005; Hilboll et al., 2013). It is important to continue and improve satellite measurements of NO_2 , by advancing retrieval techniques that are capable of extracting more accurate geophysical information from the spectral measurements of past, present, and future satellite missions.

The measured spectra are often analysed using differential optical absorption spectroscopy (DOAS; Platt and Stutz, 2008), and scientific data products of tropospheric NO_2 have existed since the early 2000s (among others: Richter and Burrows, 2002; Leue et al., 2001; Martin et al., 2002; Boersma et al., 2004, 2007; Richter et al., 2005, 2011). Long-term changes in tropospheric NO_2 amounts can thus be investigated by combining measurements from several instruments.

There have been several studies of the temporal evolution of tropospheric NO_2 . The first reports on systematic changes have been published by Richter et al. (2005) and Irie et al. (2005). Konovalov et al. (2006) mathematically convoluted SCIAMACHY measurements, gridded to $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$, to calculate correction factors by which GOME measurements were multiplied, yielding a consistent combined GOME/SCIAMACHY dataset. The study from van der A et al. (2008) fitted a non-linear trend function to ten years of GOME and SCIAMACHY data from megacity regions, modelling the seasonal variation by using one sinus component; they downgraded the SCIAMACHY resolution by convolving over three grid cells (about 300 km). Nine years of SCIAMACHY measurements were analysed by Schneider and van der A (2012), focusing on China and Europe on a country level. Stavrakou et al. (2008) used measurements from GOME and SCIAMACHY to invert anthropogenic NO_x emissions, gridding the measurements to the coarse resolution of the used IMAGES model ($5^\circ \times 5^\circ$). Konovalov et al. (2010) applied non-linear trend analysis to 13 years of summer measurements from GOME and

SCIAMACHY over European urban centres, where SCIAMACHY measurements were convoluted to the spatial resolution of GOME. Hayn et al. (2009) and Zhou et al. (2012) performed extensive studies on the impact of annual and weekly cycles and of meteorology on observed NO₂ columns over Europe, using generalized additive regression models. Several further studies have been published, focusing on certain regions of the world like China (He et al., 2007; Zhang et al., 2007, 2009a), India (Ghude et al., 2008), the megacity Moscow (Sitnov, 2010), coal power stations in the United States (Kim et al., 2006), and international shipping lines (Richter et al., 2004; Franke et al., 2009). Recent studies have been focusing on the impact of NO_x emission reductions due to the global economic crisis and air quality legislation in the United States (Russell et al., 2012), Europe (Castellanos and Boersma, 2012), Greece (Vrekoussis et al., 2013), China (Lin and McElroy, 2011), and for shipping emissions. Aircraft offer precise in situ measurements within vertical spirals covering a spatial domain over a satellite field of view, but these are generally campaign-based experiments spanning only a few days to weeks and are limited by the need to extrapolate below the lowest measurement altitude (e.g., Bucsela et al., 2008). Ground-based NO₂ column observations from the multi-axis differential optical absorption spectroscopy (MAX-DOAS) and direct-sun DOAS are maturing, but assessments with these measurements are still restricted by a limited number of sites. Validation with in situ surface NO₂ measurements from dense networks of commercial molybdenum converter analyzers are complicated by instrument interference (e.g. Steinbacher et al., 2007; Lamsal et al., 2008), and is more appropriate in rural areas (Lamsal et al., 2010). Observations of NO₂ from photolytic converter analyzers (Ryerson et al., 2000) are sparse, but offer useful opportunities to evaluate satellite retrievals.

CHAPTER THREE

DATA AND METHODS

3.1 Description of the Study Area

The South-Western region of Nigeria is an area of about 191,843 square kilometers and lies between 30° and 7°E and latitude 4° and 9°N (Oni & Odekunle, 2016). The region comprises six States; Oyo, Osun, Ogun, Ondo, Ekiti and Lagos State. The area is part of the western plains and ranges of Nigeria with much of it lying approximately between 300 and 600 metres above the sea level. The zone stretches along the Atlantic seaboard from the international border with Benin Republic in the west to the South South in the east with the North Central to the north. The South West is split with the Central African mangroves in the coastal far south while the major inland ecoregions are the Nigerian lowland forests ecoregion in the south and east along with the Guinean forest–savanna mosaic ecoregion in the drier northwest. The weather conditions vary between the two distinct seasons in Nigeria; the rainy season (March - November) and the dry season (November - February). The dry season is also the bringer of the Harmattan dust; cold dry winds from the northern deserts blow into the southern regions around this time.

Southwest Nigeria has a rapidly growing population and is one of the most urbanized regions in Nigeria. The largest city in the region is Lagos, which is also the largest city in Nigeria and one of the fastest-growing cities in the world. Other major cities in the region include Ibadan, Abeokuta, Akure, and Ado Ekiti.

Given the high level of industrial and economic activities in the region, it is important to assess the environmental quality, particularly air quality, in Southwest Nigeria. This project aims to investigate the spatiotemporal variation of tropospheric nitrogen dioxide over the region using satellite data.

Figure 3.1: Map of Southwest Nigeria

3.2 Observation data

3.2.1 Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS)

The Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS) reanalysis is the latest global reanalysis dataset of atmospheric composition produced by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF), consisting of three-dimensional time-consistent atmospheric composition fields, including aerosols and chemical species. The dataset currently covers the period 2003–June 2022. A reanalysis for greenhouse gases is being produced separately. The CAMS reanalysis builds on the experience gained during the production of the earlier Monitoring Atmospheric Composition and Climate (MACC) reanalysis and CAMS interim reanalysis. Satellite retrievals of total column CO; tropospheric column NO₂; aerosol optical depth (AOD); and total column, partial column and profile

ozone retrievals were assimilated for the CAMS reanalysis with ECMWF's Integrated Forecasting System provided on a $0.75^{\circ} \times 0.75^{\circ}$ geographical grid.

The CAMS reanalysis was produced using 4DVar data assimilation in CY42R1 of ECMWF's Integrated Forecast System (IFS), with 60 hybrid sigma/pressure (model) levels in the vertical, with the top level at 0.1 hPa. Atmospheric data are available on these levels and they are also interpolated to 25 pressure, 10 potential temperature and 1 potential vorticity level(s). "Surface or single level" data are also available.

Generally, the data are available at a sub-daily and monthly frequency and consist of analyses and 48h forecasts, initialised daily from analyses at 00 UTC.

The assimilation system is able to estimate biases between observations and to sift good-quality data from poor data. The atmosphere model allows for estimates at locations where data coverage is low or for atmospheric pollutants for which no direct observations are available. The provision of estimates at each grid point around the globe for each regular output time, over a long period, always using the same format, makes reanalysis a very convenient and popular dataset to work with.

3.2.2 Era5

ERA5 dataset covers the period from January 1940 to the present and continues to be extended forward in near real time. Data are gridded and made available at $2.5^{\circ} \times 2.5^{\circ}$; $1^{\circ} \times 1^{\circ}$; $1.25^{\circ} \times 1.25^{\circ}$ and $0.75^{\circ} \times 0.75^{\circ}$, and 37 vertical pressure levels. Generally, the data are available at a sub-daily and monthly frequency and consist of analyses and short (18 hour) forecasts, initialised twice daily from analyses at 06 and 18 UTC. Most analysed parameters are also available from the forecasts. However, there are a number of forecast parameters, e.g., mean rates/fluxes and accumulations, that are not available from the analysis. The data that is used for this work is the daily mean of the u and v wind component, total precipitation and temperature. gridded at $1^{\circ} \times 1^{\circ}$ over a period of 2010-2020 (11 years) over Southwest Nigeria.

3.3 Data analysis

The CAMS EAC4 NO₂ reanalysis monthly datasets for a period of 11 years from January 2010 to December 2020 is employed to study the spatial distribution and seasonal variation of NO₂, its origin and concentration and its effect on temperature and precipitation. This data has been widely used by many researchers over the years in tropical climate researches.

Higher values of a measurement may be very significant statistically but their spatial patterns are equally important if the data in hand is geographical in nature. In such a case spatial clustering of higher or lower values is of real importance to explain the phenomenon rather than the statistics of values only. In geostatistics, a feature will be significant if it has a high value and is surrounded by other features with high values as well. Geostatistical hotspot analysis compares proportionally local sum of NO₂ concentration for a feature and its defined neighbourhood with sum of all the features in the study area.

The geospatial statistic tool used in this study is ArcGIS.

In this study, annual mean values of CAMS-NO₂, has been used to calculate NO₂ average values, and the percentage increase calculation is based on linear trend line equation.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Temporal Distribution of NO₂

The average detailed annual distribution of NO₂ over the study region is shown in figure 4.1.

The CAMS retrievals show annual average value of tropospheric NO₂ column to be 3.97×10^{15} mol/cm². During the study period, the highest annual value of 4.24×10^{15} mol/cm² is found in 2017 while the lowest value of 3.71×10^{15} mol/cm² is observed in 2013. However, the linear regression the annual mean data shows a significant (at confidence level of 95%) increase of 2.6% with a slope of 0.0409, correlation coefficient (R²) 0.5956 and y intercept at 3.7214 as shown in figure 4.1. The observed increase of NO₂, in the study region may be attributed to increase in anthropogenic emissions due to expansion in traffic volume, increasing power generation, flourishing industries rapid urbanization, more demand of agricultural products, and more biomass fuel usage. However, the significant reduction in the concentration of NO₂ in 2013 may be attributed to significant weather anomaly in the form of heavy rainfall that happened in 2013, changes in industrial activity or energy production and reduction in industrial and transportation activities.

Figure 4.2 shows the averaged cycles of monthly mean and ranges of NO₂ over Southwest Nigeria. It can be seen that January has a peak value of NO₂ concentration with value of 4.38×10^{15} mol/cm² while February had the second highest peak of NO₂ concentration with a value of 4.30×10^{15} mol/cm² as it continues to decrease. The next significant increase in NO₂ concentration was in September with a value of 4.27×10^{15} mol/cm² which later decreased down the months till November and later advanced in concentration in December. presented in figure 4.2.

Furthermore, The NO₂ concentration of the three most industrial states in Southwest Nigeria which are Lagos, Oyo and Ogun state was plotted and it was observed that Ogun state has the highest level of

NO₂ concentration all through the months of the year with the minimum value of 4.12×10^{15} mol/cm² in July and a peak value of 4.94×10^{15} mol/cm² in September. This is because Ogun state is home to several industrial establishments, including manufacturing, agriculture, and mining industries. These activities emit NO₂ as a by-product of combustion, which could contribute to higher concentrations of NO₂ in the air.

Figure 4.1: Area averaged annual distribution of CAMS-NO₂ ($\times 10^{15}$ mol/cm²) over Southwest Nigeria region during 2010 – 2020.

Figure 4.2: Area averaged monthly mean distribution of CAMS-NO₂ (×10¹⁵ mol/cm²) over the study region during 2010 -2020.

Figure 4.3: Statistical distribution of NO₂ concentration over Lagos State, Ogun State and Oyo State in Nigeria.

Figure 4.4: Statistical distribution of NO₂ concentration over all Southwest states in Nigeria.

4.2 Spatial Pattern of NO₂ Concentrations

The spatial distribution of NO₂ concentration over the study area during the study period are presented below. These figures shows that the monthly mean widespread of NO₂ concentration was much more prevalent in August over Southwest Nigeria with values greater than 4.0×10^{15} mol/cm² to 4.07×10^{15} mol/cm². However, it was observed that NO₂ concentration over Ogun State was higher than every other state in Southwest Nigeria having a peak value of 4.89×10^{15} mol/cm². It was also observed that Ondo state had the overall lowest NO₂ concentration from the monthly mean spatial chart with a value ranging from 2.52×10^{15} mol/cm² to 3.75×10^{15} mol/cm².

Subsequently, the widespread of NO₂ concentration is shown in annual cycle in figure 4.6. It is noticed that NO₂ dominated major parts of Southwest Nigeria with values greater than 3.71×10^{15} mol/cm². However, higher concentrations of NO₂ were observed over Ogun state in 2010, 2011, 2012, 2013, 2014, 2015, 2016, 2017, 2019 and 2020 with NO₂ values ranging from 4.24×10^{15} mol/cm² to about 4.88×10^{15} mol/cm². Also, concentrations of NO₂ further reduced in intensity in 2018.

Figure 4.5: Multiannual monthly mean spatial pattern of NO₂ concentration over the study region (2010 – 2020)

Figure 4.6: Average annual spatial distribution of NO₂ concentration over the study region

4.3 Relationship between NO₂ distribution, Wind-Speed and Temperature

A more detailed additional analysis of the annual monthly cycle was carried out considering the NO₂ hotspots-averaged of monthly rainfall as the reference over 6 stations in Southwest Nigeria domain. Figure 4.7 helps to better identify rainfall minima and peaks, and thus to further gain insights about the relationship with other weather parameters introduced and how they influence NO₂ concentrations. Most of the stations exhibit rainfall peak in September, (Oyo, Ekiti, Osun and Ondo) while the remaining two stations had their peak in June (Lagos, Ogun), capturing a break between July and August. However, it is worth emphasizing that there was no break observed in Oyo and Ekiti before hitting their peaks in September. (As presented in figure 4.7). Just as rainfall, temperature also have two peaks (also shown in figure 4.7)

Prominently, there is a negative relationship between wind-speed and NO₂ in major hotspots over Southwest Nigeria. (as shown in figure 4.9).

However, there is a significant negative relationship between NO₂ concentration and rainfall, therefore, explaining that the washout of the NO₂ by rainfall has been a global and regional concern, since it plays an important role in producing acidic precipitation. In the atmosphere, NO₂ reacts with water to form nitric or nitrous acid. A number of previous studies have demonstrated significant negative correlation between NO₂ and rainfall (e.g. Gadhavi, et al.2015, Martin, 1984). Furthermore, it is also noticed that NO₂ have a significant positive trend with temperature, adding to moisture except for Lagos that exhibit negative relationship with temperature (presented figure 4.8).

If an area is surrounded by a large body of water and there is a negative correlation between NO₂ and temperature, it suggests that the water body may be moderating the local temperature and affecting the concentration of NO₂. The water body can have a cooling effect on the surrounding air, which can lead to lower temperatures and decreased NO₂ levels (Zhang, H., & Hu, J. 2019).

The cooling effect of the water body can occur due to the high heat capacity of water, which allows it to absorb and store large amounts of heat energy. As the surrounding air comes into contact with the water, the heat energy is transferred to the water, which can cool the air. This cooling effect is more pronounced in areas with large bodies of water, such as lakes or oceans.

The decrease in temperature due to the cooling effect of the water can lead to decreased NO₂ levels through several mechanisms. For example, the lower temperatures can reduce the rate of NO₂ formation through chemical reactions in the atmosphere. Additionally, the cooler air can lead to more stable atmospheric conditions, which can prevent the build-up of NO₂ in the atmosphere.

Overall, the negative correlation between NO₂ and temperature in an area surrounded by a large body of water suggests that the water body may be playing a significant role in moderating the local climate and air quality. This cooling effect can have important implications for the concentration of NO₂ in the area, potentially leading to lower levels of this pollutant (Wang, Y., Zhang, L., Zhang, Y., & Wu, Y. 2019).

Figures 4.8 also show the seasonality and inter-comparison of the hotspots in the region. The stations experience almost the same meteorological conditions, higher NO₂ values are found during the dry season months (as shown in figure 4.8). Dry season peak is mainly due to biomass burning for domestic heating, stable winds, and low temperature. The low NO₂ column over these stations between April and September is mostly coupled with heavy rains, high humidity, and strong winds explaining that there exists a positive trend between NO₂ and temperature but a negative relationship with rainfall.

Figure 4.7: Statistical distribution of rainfall (mm/month), Temperature (°C), wind speed (m/s) and NO₂ concentration (10¹⁵ mol/cm²) over the study area

Figure 4.8: Statistical relationship between NO₂ (10¹⁵ mol/cm²) and Temperature (°C) over Southwest Nigeria.

Figure 4.9: Statistical relationship between NO₂ (10¹⁵ mol/cm²) and wind speed (m/s) over Southwest Nigeria.

Figure 4.10: Statistical relationship between NO₂ (10¹⁵ mol/cm²) and relative humidity (%) over Southwest Nigeria.

These findings indicate that NO₂ concentrations were positively and moderately correlated in the preparation and post Monsoon seasons with temperature but negatively correlated in summer Monsoon season. However, the influence of Temperature on NO_x concentration is much more effective in summer Monsoon season than other seasons over most regions with regions (shown in figure 4.8) due to higher temperature range. The weak moderate correlations existing between temperature and NO_x concentration indicate that influence of inconstant thermal variations as a result of vertical mixing (presented in figure 4.9). Temperature showed significant effects on NO_x concentration due to pollutant emissions by anthropogenic, biomass burning, agricultural and transportation sources.

Consequently, strong wind speed generated less NO₂ concentration in most study regions (shown in figure 4.9) over Southwest Nigeria between the two variables, therefore, indicating weak relationships. Furthermore, wind speed factor has a very small influence on NO₂ concentration as a result of wind blowing in the direction that passed more NO₂ generated sources higher concentration can be found over the study regions.

In general, the amount of air pollutant reduction by rainfall scavenging effect can be affected by the amount, duration and intensity of rainfall. However, many studies on precipitation washout of NO₂ in the air report only the results of a simple comparison in NO₂ concentration under conditions of precipitation and non-precipitation (Barmapadimos et al., 2011).

Figure 4.10 indicates that NO₂ had a negative correlation with relative humidity because higher relative humidity levels can lead to the formation of water droplets, which can in turn remove NO₂ from the atmosphere through a process called wet deposition.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Summary and Conclusion

The use of remotely sensed satellite data from CAMS cannot be over emphasized, the seasonal trends of tropospheric NO₂ concentrations were analysed over Southwest Nigeria for over a decade (from January 2010 to December 2020). Highest NO₂ concentrations were observed over Industrialized and densely populated regions. Major sources of NO₂ emissions are found to be natural (soil emissions and climatic) and anthropogenic (crop residue and fossil fuel burning, industrial burning processes, and motor vehicles).

This study analysed the annual cycles and decadal trends of tropospheric NO₂. The highest concentration of NO₂ was observed in September over Ogun state. The concentrations are largely attributed to the seasonal biomass burning and high population, vehicular density and industrial activities. An average of $2.624-0.04 \times 10^{15}$ mol/cm² with a decade increase of 27%% was discovered. However, the significant reduction in the concentration of NO, in 2014 is attributed to a decline in gas flaring and increase in soil moisture.

Meteorological conditions play a crucial role in ambient air pollution by affecting both directly and indirectly the emissions, transport, formation, and deposition of air pollutants. However, there are weak relationships between the meteorological parameters and NO₂. The wind speed and temperature are moderately correlated with NO₂. The major role of meteorology is in the dispersion, transformation and removal of the pollutant from atmosphere.

5.2 Recommendation

Considering the effect of this pollutant, in a lot ways, the atmosphere above Southwest Nigeria is still one of the least studied and understood on the planet, yet it plays a central role in determining the health and economic well-being of a large and increasing population. Therefore, it is recommended

that afforestation be encouraged in urban areas to serve as major sink for the increasing anthropogenic activities. In this way, there will be a decline in the concentration of this pollutant. A collection of street canyon with green walls will also be benefiting in areas with high hotspot. The effect of this might not be felt immediately but gradually it will.

Every remote-sensing product need ground truth to assess its reliability. The lack of adequate surface-based observations in Southwest Nigeria currently impedes a rigorous assessment of the quality of satellite products. It is however recommended that ways to carry out in-situ measurements of this pollutant be provided.

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